

Family Types and Academic Achievement of Senior Secondary School Students in Yenagoa Educational Zone of Bayelsa State.

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Abstract

The present study was conducted to assess four family types to see if difference existed in the third term examination result scores of students in classes SSI and SSII in Yenagoa Educational Zone based on these four family types. To this end, four objectives guided the study and descriptive survey was used as the study's design. The study's population consist of (9,777) students from 34 senior secondary schools. The research used multi stage sampling technique to draw the sample size. Firstly, simple random technique was used to select 10 schools with a population of 3,003 students, then using proportionate sampling technique 10% of the total number of students in SS I and SS II in each of the selected schools gave a sample of 300 students. Data were collected using researcher developed questionnaire titled family type questionnaire (FTQ) and student's third term examination result scores obtained from sample schools. Test re-test technique was applied to ascertain the dependability of the first instrument which gave a coefficient of 0.71. The hypotheses were tested at the 0.05 alpha using analysis of variance. Analysis of the data indicated that statistically there is substantial disparity in academic achievement of students in English Language (F-ratio33.988) on alpha level of .000 on the basis of family type. The results posited that parent, teachers, government and counsellors should offer the essential assistance and support for students from polygamous, extended and single parent family types to overcome poor academic achievement.

Keywords: Family Types, Third Term Examinations, Poor Academic Achievement, and Parents

Introduction

Education's significance is immeasurable. No nation can afford to disregard education, as it is the foundation for a productive life in any society. This is because it is the primary source of human resources required for any country's scientific, technological and socio-economic advancement. Despite this, there has been a significant amount of discussion about secondary school students' academic performance. From observation it seems some individuals agree that the decline in education standards poses a significant threat to the nation's future human resource generation. The majority of secondary school students encounter academic challenges that manifest themselves in the form of academic performance. Some researchers such as Gabriel (2013), Nuttall, Nuttal, Polit and Hunter (2000), Hetherington and Parke (1993), Onyi (2002) have endeavored to identify the causes of the decline in the academic performance of secondary school students.

The consequence of this persistently poor academic performance of students is that a significant number of them may not achieve the grades necessary to advance to higher education institutes. This has caused concern among well-intentioned Nigerians, parents, researchers, and educators. As a result, it is imperative that efforts be directed toward the development of an enduring remedy for students' under performance in senior secondary institutions. In order to achieve this objective, researchers have identified numerous factors that lead to poor performance particularly in Senior Secondary Certificate Examinations. Several of these factors include the absence of teachers, the overloading of syllabuses, poor educational facilities such as laboratories, the lethargy, the poor attitude and dearth of interest of the students, the insufficient teaching methods of the tutors, the large class size, and the family size and family background of the students. There is no doubt that the child's academic achievement could be facilitated or impeded by the family's social climate, given its significant implication on the child and its role as a key agent of socialization. Although numerous educators maintain that family influences childrens' academic performance and that education begins at home, there has been a dearth of empirical research in recent years to substantiate this assertion, particularly in Bayelsa.

From observation, there seem to be cases where a man is married to two, three wives (Polygynous) specially in the rural areas and they barely seem to provide for the wives and the children because they lack the resources to do so and rather than looking for ways to support these women, they go after other women compounding their problems the more. In such family types, every wife is left to take the responsibility for her own children's feeding, clothing, and education, etc. Some do petty trading while some go as far as going to fishing camps or farm settlements to do fishing and farming after which they come out to the towns to sell their farm produce like (fish, plantain, cassava, snail, crayfish, periwinkles) in other to get themselves the things they need. Children from these homes grow up to be violent, unstable emotionally, truants, wayward, robbers, and cultists, and in some cases, they never even attend school.

Some children take up menial jobs to fend for themselves and by so doing become distracted in their studies while others end up leaving school because parents may lack the resources to provide their basic needs both the in and out of school. Especially for those in school provision of educational materials such as (text books, exercise books, school bags and shoes), payment of fees as at when due, and all these requires money which is limited in such families, hence the educational challenge for children. Here peer pressure comes in, at this point children might be pressured by their peers to go into social vices that are against the acceptable norms and values of the society and this may lead to low academic achievement as such activities may likely distract them from their studies.

This is in line with the views of Adesehinwa (2013) who determined the impact of family type and insufficient financing on students' educational attainment. One will want to ask what becomes of these children in the future, because they are the future of the society? If the future leaders perform badly in schools today or some do not even go to school or are drop-outs and lack the right morals, norms, values and the capacity to lead the nation in the future as a result of their family type, then what becomes of even the society at large? In every society, the family serves as a social unit and provides children with early experiences and stimulation (Collins, 2007). The family makes an

initial impact on a youngster that may stick with them for the rest of their lives. According to Ekanem (2004), children tend to imitate their parents, siblings, and the objects in their immediate surroundings. These individuals might have a positive or negative impact on their self-esteem and ability to learn.

Therefore, if the family is faulty what becomes of the children and the society at large? Reducing school failure and low educational attainment benefits society and individuals alike, as educated people support more democratic societies and lasting economies, are less dependent on government support, and are less susceptible to economic recessions. Societies with trained people are well equipped to handle present and future potential crises, as well as promote economic growth and societal development. Therefore, this study is necessary to gather accurate and up-to-date data on the degree to which different family types influence educational success of students in Bayelsa.

The basic aim of this study therefore, is to ascertain the extent to which various family types determine academic achievement of Senior Secondary one and two (SS 1&2) students' in Yenagoa Educational Zone of Bayelsa State.

Statement of the Problem

These days, instructors are often held accountable for the poor academic achievement of their pupils without really looking into other relevant aspects that may be causing the issue. The government, parents, educators, and students place mutual blame for the low academic achievement of pupils. Parents accuse educators of being unmotivated to do their work. Government and teachers blame parents for not helping their children complete their homework; teachers blame the government for paying them poorly, which deters them from teaching; parents blame the government for not providing learning resources to schools; and students blame the government for their lack of self-discipline and commitment to studies. As far as academic accomplishment is concerned, most individuals are fast at pointing fingers at both the kid and the instructor. Should all the blame for poor academic performance/attainment of educational goals go to the educators, who always appear to want the best for their students? It is often believed that a child's socialization begins at home. Children spend a greater amount of time at home than at school.

Numerous family-related characteristics, including family size and type, may have played a role in the pupils' high or poor accomplishments. The nature of the family may have an impact on a student's academic performance in one or more ways. For example, in a nuclear family, the parents may be able to devote enough time to their child to foster improved academic performance. On the other hand, if the family is extended, parents may not have enough time to attend to the educational needs of their children. More so, the house may be even too rowdy for the children to even concentrate to study and do good homework which may lead to poor academic achievement. Presently, there are in Bayelsa State family types, such as Nuclear, Extended, Polygamous and Single parent family. It is believed that some of these family types may be positively or negatively related to the academic achievement of Senior Secondary school students in Bayelsa State.

This study therefore focuses on family types as determinants of academic achievement of senior secondary school students in Yenagoa Educational Zone, Bayelsa State. The findings of this study will likely fill existing literature gap.

Purpose of the Study

The purpose of this study is to investigate family types as determinants of educational attainment of students in English Language in selected senior secondary schools in Bayelsa State. Specifically, the study seeks to find out if:

1. Nuclear family type determines academic achievement of students in English Language in senior secondary schools in Yenagoa Educational Zone in Bayelsa State.
2. Extended family type determines academic achievement of students in English Language in senior secondary schools in Yenagoa Educational Zone in Bayelsa State.
3. Polygamous family type determines academic achievement of students in English Language in senior secondary schools in Yenagoa Educational Zone in Bayelsa State.
4. Single parent family type determines academic achievement of students in English Language in senior secondary schools in Yenagoa Educational Zone in Bayelsa State.

Research Questions

The research provided responses to the questions below:

1. To what extent does nuclear family determine academic achievement of students in English Language in senior secondary schools in Yenagoa Educational Zone in Bayelsa State?
2. To what extent does extended family determine academic achievement of students in English Language in senior secondary schools in Yenagoa Educational Zone in Bayelsa State?
3. To what extent does polygamous family determine academic achievement of students in English Language in senior secondary schools in Yenagoa Educational Zone in Bayelsa State?
4. To what extent does a single parent family determine academic achievement of students in English Language in senior secondary schools in Yenagoa Educational Zone in Bayelsa State?

Hypotheses

The following hypotheses are for this study.

1. There is no statistically significant difference in students' academic achievement in English Language on the basis of family types.

Methodology

The research applied descriptive survey research design in examining family types as determinants of educational success of students in English Language in Senior Secondary schools in Yenagoa educational zone. The population of the study consists of all the senior secondary class one – class two (SS1- 2) students in thirty-four (34) public secondary schools in Yenagoa educational zone. These thirty-four (34) schools have a population of nine thousand seven hundred and seventy-

seven (9,777) students. (Source: Bayelsa State Post Primary Schools Board students' enrollment, Department of Planning, Research and Statistics).

For even representation, multi-stage random sampling technique was used to select the desired sample from the population of the study. Multi-stage random sampling according to Asike (2012) is a sampling technique that requires the researcher to choose his samples in stages until the desired sample is obtained. With simple random sampling procedure ten (10) schools were drawn from the total number of schools. The researcher listed all the thirty-four (34) secondary schools in Yenagoa educational zone, then rolled each slip of the listed schools into a ball, mixed the papers well into a container and shook it properly. The first-picked ten (10) paper balls from the container were chosen as the sample secondary schools for the study.

Using proportionate sampling technique, a total of three hundred (300) students, 10% of the total number of students in SS I & SS II which comprise of three thousand three students (3,003) approximated to 3000 in each of the 10 selected schools made up the sample.

An instrument titled family type and academic achievement questionnaire was drafted which sought information on the students' family type. Also, to determine academic achievement, terminal exam scores of students in English Language was obtained from the school authorities from all sample schools.

A total of 288 questionnaires out of 300 administered were retrieved 12 not retrieved.

The mean and standard deviation were used to analyze the study questions, and analysis of variance was employed to evaluate the hypotheses at 0.05 alpha. The null hypothesis was rejected because the F ratio value of (F- ratio 33.988) for English Language and alpha level of .000 is less than 0.05 Alpha level

Results and Discussion

In this chapter, results from data analyzed are presented on the basis of the research questions and hypotheses that guided the study.

Analysis of Research Questions

The results obtained from analysis of research questions 1-4 are presented in table 1.

Table 1: Academic achievement of students from different family types.

Family types	No.	Mean	SD	Minimum score	Maximum score	Mean percentage
Nuclear family	55	54.89	11.31	14	72	76%
Extended family	66	33.59	10.22	00	49	68%
Polygamous family	115	37.51	13.11	00	86	43%
Single parent family	52	36.01	15.57	7	86	42%

Table 1: reveals that Nuclear statistics (M= 54.89.59, SD=11.31) imply 76% performance rate in English Language by students, making the highest impact. While the lowest impact is that of the single parent family type with 42% and statistics of (M= 36.01, SD= 15.57).

Analysis of Research Hypotheses

Research Hypotheses One: There is no statistically significant difference in students’ academic achievement in English Language on the basis of family types.

Table 2: Analysis of variance for family type and students’ academic achievement in English Language.

Source	df	Some of Squares	Mean Square	F Ratio	Significance
Between groups	3	16409.319	5469.773	33.988	.000*
Within Groups	284	45705.011	160.933		
Total	287	62114.330			

P < 0.05

Findings in table 2 shows that family types significantly determine students’ academic achievement in English Language (F ratio = 33.988 on alpha level of 000. Moreover there is a statistically significant difference in the mean score of the groups with the Nuclear family having the best performance.

Multiple comparisons

To ascertain which family type mostly impacts to the significant disparity, a Post Hoc Test was done.

Table 3: Multiple Comparisons. Scheffe

*The mean difference is significant at the 0.05 level.

Post Hoc Test was utilized to also locate where substantial disparity between the family types used in the research was highest in terms of mean variance. The results from the table above shows that,

Dependent Variable	(I) Family type	(J) family type	Mean Difference (I-J)	Std. Error	Sig.	95% Confidence Interval	
						Lower Bound	Upper Bound
English score	Extended family	Nuclear family	-21.30000*	2.31613	.000	-27.8137	-14.7863
		Single family	-2.42832	2.35229	.785	-9.0437	4.1873
		Polygamous family	-3.92213	-1.95903	.263	-9.4316	1.5873
	Nuclear family	Extended family	21.30000*	2.31613	.000	14.7863	27.8137
		Single family	18.87168*	2.45376	.000	11.9709	25.7724
		Polygamous family	17.37787*	2.07978	.000	11.5289	23.2269
	Single parent family	Extended family	2.42832	2.35229	.785	-4.1871	9.0437
		Nuclear family	-18.87168*	2.45376	.000	-25.7724	-11.9709
		Polygamous family	-1.49381	2.11997	.920	-7.4559	4.4682
	Polygamous family	Extended family	3.92213	1.95903	.263	-1.5873	9.4316
		Nuclear family	-17.37787*	2.07978	.000	-23.2269	-11.5289
		Single parent family	1.49381	2.11997	.920	-4.4682	7.4559

the mean disparity between extended and nuclear family type was -21.30000. The mean disparity among extended and single parent family type was -2.42832. The mean dissimilarity among extended and polygamous family type was -3.92213. The mean disparity between nuclear and single parent family type was 18.87168. The mean difference between nuclear and polygamous family type was -1.49381. While the mean disparity among single parents and polygamous family type was -1.49381.

In Table 3 the mean variance is highest between extended and nuclear family type (-21.30000) while the least mean disparity is between single parent and polygamous family type (-1.49381) respectively.

Discussion of findings.

The outcome of this investigation is compared and contrasted with those of previous empirical investigations conducted by other scholars. Therefore, the above serve as the basis for these conversations.

Findings from this study also revealed that students from the nuclear family type have the highest academic achievement with 76% performance level in English Language than their counterparts in extended, polygamous and single parent family types. Results of this findings are summarized in table 1. This may be due to the fact there is a possibility that children from nuclear families tend to relate and gather insight from their parents due to the small nature or size of the family. This is consistent with the findings of Nwachukwu (2002), who said that children's academic success decreased with increasing family size.

Furthermore, findings from this study revealed that children from polygamous family have 43% performance in English. This low achievement may be due to the fact that polygamous family are more prone than their peers to suffer from greater psychological issues from nuclear family type. These psychological problems invariably affect their educational success in school. This is also consistent with the findings of Ogbemudia and Aiasa (2013), who suggested that children's academic success is influenced by the physical and psychological state of their family environment.

Findings from this study also revealed that children from extended family type have 68% performance in English Language which is also not as high as that of children from Nuclear family type. This low performance may be due to the fact that the extended family type is usually large like that of polygamous family with parents having too much responsibilities that they may barely have time to assist their children with their school work and also provide for them their basic scholastic materials due to insufficient fund and resources.

Also, findings from this study revealed that children from single parent homes have 42% performance in English Language (see table 1) which is the lowest among the other family types. The reason for their low performance could be as a result of the one parent figure in the family. A child from a single parent family suffers one parent deprivation and most times a single parent finds it difficult to provide the needs of the children both educationally and otherwise. This is consistent with research by Uwaifo (2008) on the impact of motherhood and family structure on the academic achievement of Nigerian university students.

Findings obtained from testing of hypotheses one revealed that the null hypotheses was rejected because table 2 shows that statistically family types significantly determine students' academic achievement in English Language (F- ratio 33.988) on alpha level of .000.

Furthermore, there is a variance in the mean score of the categories, with the Nuclear family exhibiting the most exceptional performance. This suggests that, in secondary schools in the Yenagoa educational zone of Bayelsa State, there is a statistically significant variation in pupils' academic success in English language based on family types. This is in line with the findings of Gabriel's (2013) study, which contends that a child's family type often affects their academic achievement.

Conclusion

The study findings indicate that the kind of family a kid comes from—nuclear, extended, polygamous, or single—has a substantial influence on their scholastic achievement. Therefore, it is the responsibility of parents, guardians, and other adults to provide a safe, orderly, and supportive home environment for their children's academic development and advancement in the classroom, at home, and in life in general.

Recommendations

The recommendations made in light of the results of this investigation were:

1. Parents should preserve their marriages and family structures in order to be excellent role models for their wards and future generations.
2. Keeping in mind the expenses of a comfortable lifestyle for both themselves and their children, parents need to preserve family kinds and sizes that they can successfully sponsor and manage.
3. Parents should be made aware of the need of raising small families so they can meet their children's educational demands and inspire them to study well and do well in government.

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